

USE OF INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING FORTEPIANO IN MUSIC INSTITUTIONS

Rakhimova Mavludakhan Nabijanovna

Teacher of the "Music Education" department of the Faculty of Arts,
Andijan State University

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Abstract: This article discusses the scientific and practical importance of using innovative methods and technologies in teaching piano science to students in the educational process of music education and art education institutions.

Key words: Educational system, musical art, lesson, piano, computer, quiz, teenager.

"Let's put the key in the hands of musically inclined children to enter the magical garden of music to enhance the meaning of their whole life" **Zoltan Koday**

Introduction.

Music and art teachers are a large group of educated, experienced and highly qualified professionals who teach and educate children and adolescents, opening a beautiful and high world to them. Looking into the inner world of each student and revealing his creative individuality is the task of teachers, which modern educational technologies help to solve.

They not only help to develop creative imagination, improve performance skills of students, but also allow to conduct great research work. And if you add your own genuine interest in the endless possibilities of the Internet, student research, making students their own creative partners, learning with and sometimes with children, you will be enthusiastic if you do, then our work will always be successful [5; 67].

The introduction of computer teaching technologies into the educational process increases the effectiveness and efficiency of teaching, creates an active environment for the education of the child's personality. Computer education is now considered as a pedagogical technology. It is necessary to take into account the current trends in education, which are focused on the intensity of education and creativity. It is important to have new technologies and sources of information to interest students, to increase motivation for piano science and to increase the results of pedagogical activities.

Using computers in piano lessons.

The use of computers in music education provides a high level of visibility, supports and develops knowledge, skills and abilities, helps to organize various forms of creativity in the lesson. The use of music and computer technology in the piano class is one of the methods of forming a child's personality [1; 54].

In order to optimize the learning process in the piano class, it is useful to use media materials in the character, image, content, performance style of the musical piece, in the preparation of the students' independent works, competitions, and speeches at concerts. These are: pictures, albums, books, architecture, music collections, audio, video recordings, quiz questions.

Learners about composers, musical works studied in class, the style of performance of these works, the historical period in which the composers lived, visual materials: portraits of

composers, various pictures of nature, photos and illustrations of musical instruments, didactic cards for various sections of musical literacy information will be provided. If earlier a lot of effort was spent on collecting information and visual aids, now thanks to the computer, there are huge opportunities to collect media materials, and all this is colorful, attractive and interesting for students.

Using computer technology, piano teaching becomes more effective. Computer programs activate the development of imagination, thinking, musical perception; the use of new information technologies helps to create clear images, makes students' abstract knowledge more meaningful, as a result of which students' creative activity is activated.

Thus, the use of new information technologies helps to activate cognitive activity, increase the effectiveness and efficiency of the lesson, and allows students to self-educate. New information technologies increase students' motivation for piano lessons, affect the development of the child's personality and reveal children's creative potential [3; 79].

It should be noted that the use of computer technology can help in the initial training, which is one of the most important in the professional education of a musician. The most important of the initial tasks is to inspire the child with the desire to learn the language of music without separating it from the game stage appropriate for his age, it is necessary to build the lesson in the form of an interesting game.

The computer will help us in this. It is worth using musical materials, drawings, piano puzzles, riddles, musical quizzes in the educational process. I would like to highlight the educational video lessons for children. In them, musical literacy is presented to the child in a colorful and bright language, which allows the student to master the material faster.

Of course, the computer is a teacher's assistant, but it should not completely replace it. The educational process is based on pedagogical technologies. The computer is entrusted with activities that supplement the activity of the teacher.

Use of Internet resources in training.

The term computer science scares many people. We have always been proud of the human factor in the upbringing of a musician, a subtle penetration into the soul. At the same time, new directions do not always exclude the peaceful existence of everything that is traditionally recognized, while at the same time providing many clear advantages to today's art school.

Using Internet resources, high school students can, for example, compose an in-depth essay on content and content, find unique materials, interesting facts, find sources that have been forgotten for many reasons [2; 45].

You can engage students from elementary grades to work with innovative technologies. It's no secret that our young schoolchildren have computers and can often use the Internet without the help of their parents. It is very important to be able to competently form the motivation to create a presentation, for example, to master the elements of musical literacy or to listen to the performance of the studied work, to watch the portraits of great composers.

In middle and high schools, you can offer the use of Internet resources to find the necessary notes on websites, listen to the studied work in different performances. Such work helps to acquire new knowledge, develop the ability to analyze, compare and draw the necessary conclusions.

It should be noted that in addition to knowledge and skills, young musicians get positive emotions and bright impressions from classical and modern works. Thus, a symbiosis of

rational thinking and emotional perception is created, which is very important for preparing for an exam, class or school-wide concert, as well as for preparing for serious regional, local and international competitions.

Modern information computer system - what does the Internet offer? For example, computer support has long been available in the US for those who want it. If you go to the website "my school online" (that is, my school in Real Time), then you can take an interesting trip to the world of music: a huge list of places where you can start lessons for a person who wants to do music. is done [4; 167].

These are various games, a musical chronograph called "this day in the history of music", information about music and other art. And all this can be found out by pressing a certain button, without trying to find specific information. There are many breakthrough moments where the computer exists—the computer takes over routine tasks and leaves room for the user to express themselves creatively, and musical activities are no exception. In my practice, I often refer readers to certain sites on the Internet, where biographies of composers and many classical music, music of different styles and directions, as well as texts, history of the creation of various works, and audio recordings are presented. I suggest finding the material.

There are also many biographical films, cartoons, and multimedia projects about composers and performers that are useful for introducing readers.

For example: cartoon series "historical figures" one of the series is dedicated to Beethoven, animated series "little Mozart" - for junior and middle classes.

Multimedia project "Old Piano Tales" publications about Tchaikovsky, Prokofiev, Schumann, Mozart, Beethoven - for upper classes.

It is also highly recommended to watch various lectures - local and international violinist, pianist, teacher-musicologist, art critic, teacher, cultural expert. These lectures will also be interesting for teachers.

Internet contests.

I would also like to highlight extramural Internet competitions as one of the innovative ways of working with students.

Internet contests are of great help to participants who find it difficult to go to face-to-face contests (often the contests are organized in cities far from our region, financial problems, health conditions do not allow), those who want to more successfully prepare for an important speech, the Internet -participation in the contest allows you to. get individual recommendations from the jury members, what to pay attention to and what to fix first.

Summary.

The use of information technologies in the educational process creates great opportunities for the teacher in conducting lessons, makes the lesson more interesting, memorable, visual, allows new use of text, sound and video-informational parts in music lessons, enriches the methodological possibilities of the music lesson and gives it gives a modern degree. The use of information technology in music lessons has a number of important tasks, first of all, it is to increase interest in learning and educational and cognitive activities, to master educational materials, to activate cognitive activities and to realize the creative potential of students.

Music lessons should be modern, teachers should make extensive use of modern computer software, and students should use computers more to prepare for lessons, integrate materials, and answer questions about music topics. Modern computer technologies provide diversity,

availability and uniqueness of educational information unlike traditional music teaching tools. They help the teacher to make the educational process more effective and qualitative..

References:

1. Gorbunova I.B. Computers in music education. - M., RGPU, 2001.
2. Zakharova G. Information technologies in education. M., 2013.
3. Kadina G.V. "Multimedia technologies are one of the promising directions of the educational process." - M., "Music at school", issue 3, 2009.
4. Lifanovsky B. Internet for musicians. M., 2006.
5. Petrenko A.I. Multimedia. - M., Binom. 1994.
6. Ibragimov, B. (2023). Types And Importance Of Innovative Technologies In Education. Молодые ученые, 1(20), 96-98.